

BOND OF GFRP BARS IN REINFORCED CONCRETE THROUGH SPLICE IN BEAMS SUBMITTED TO BENDING

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ABSTRACT

Eight beams were moulded using self-compacting concrete (SCC) and four of them being tested: two using polyolefin fibers and two without fibers. Two different splice lengths were tested, twenty-five and forty diameters long, using GFRP Brazilian bars. The test methodology was the splice of longitudinal reinforcement in GFRP in the middle third of the beams in order to evaluate the bond stress at the interface between bars in GFRP and concrete. The conclusion is that longer splice lengths can reduce bond tension, increasing the ultimate load of the beams and that the use of polyolefin fibers increased the maximum bond tension by up to 57% and the ultimate load by up to 13%. The contribution of polyolefin fibers is more relevant for shorter splice lengths.

KEYWORDS

Bond; Splice; Polymeric Fibers; SCC.

INTRODUCTION

The use of FRP reinforcement aims to replace traditional steel reinforcement with a material that presents similar performance and greater durability, immune to corrosion, resulting in lower maintenance costs and longer life of the structures. For more than thirty years, studies involving the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) in structures have aroused the interest of researchers in various countries (ACI 440, 2015).

In Brazil, such as other countries that are already researching and using FRP reinforcement, several structures are exposed to various damaging elements, especially chloride ions from saline fogs and tide breaks in coastal regions, in the case of Brazil, or melt salts, countries subject to severe winters. Additionally, to the structures directly exposed to tide splash, such as ports, marine structures and bridges, other structures built near the coastal area are subject to salt fog, which can advance kilometers towards the interior, with the corrosion rate in marine atmosphere subject to 30 to 40 times the rate of corrosion in places with chloride-free atmosphere.

FRP reinforcement bars

FRP bars have their own characteristics, inherent in the behavior of the fibers used and the polymer matrix chosen for their manufacture. In addition, the surface shape of the bar can vary, there are various types of shapes and coatings, such as helical wrapped bars, sand coating and carved fiber blanket, among others. Thus, the bond between bar and concrete is influenced by various factors such as concrete compression resistance, microcracks of the cement matrix, bar surface shape and FRP bar elasticity module, among other factors.

The bond between concrete and reinforcement bars are critical to ensuring the load capacity of the structure. With the use of GFRP reinforcement this bar/concrete bond is given in a different way than when steel bars are used, due to the properties of the material and texture of their surface (Gooranorimi et al., 2018). The bond between bars and the concrete that surrounds them is a critical parameter that controls the behavior in service, the crack pattern, and the ultimate resistance of the structures on reinforced concrete (Zemour et al., 2018).

Use of fiber reinforced concrete (FRC) and self-compacting concrete (SCC)

The use of fiber reinforced concrete helps in the bond between the FRP reinforcement and concrete, inasmuch as they decrease the microcracks of the cement matrix and act as bridges to transfer tensions between sides of the cracked concrete matrix, decreasing the concentration of tensions in the part of the non-cracked section.

Furthermore, given that the inclusion of dispersed fibers in the cement matrix has an adverse effect on the decrease in concrete workability, this work also proposed the use of self-adhesive concrete, improving concrete workability, eliminating the thickening stage, as well as reducing the need for performance. In Almeida Filho et al. (2008) the authors conducted bond analysis between conventional, self-compacting concrete and steel bars to assess the effects of the use of self-compacting concrete on the adherence. They conclude that self-compacting concrete has the same bond as conventional concrete and therefore its use is recommended by reducing stages in the execution of armed concrete structures.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

In order to analyze the bond tension between fiber reinforced self-compacting concrete and reinforcement in GFRP, four-point flexion tests were carried out on four beams with longitudinal GFRP bar reinforcements. For this purpose, eight 2.90 m beams with a rectangular cross section of 150 mm by 250 mm were molded, varying the length of trespass in the middle third of the beams, using 25 diameters and 40 diameters and the presence or not of 60 mm long polyolefin fibers included in concrete. Concrete cover was defined as 32 mm to longitudinal reinforcement. Reinforcement scheme and test setup is represented on Figure 1.

Figure 1: reinforcement displacement and test setup

Only four of the eight beams were tested, since each specimen presented a replica, so that, in case of unexpected events during the conduct of tests, there was the possibility of testing at least one specimen representing a variable under analysis. Those replica beams are now being kept under environmental exposure, in order to analyze the effect of chloride natural atmosphere over bond of GFRP bars. It will be subject of future tests.

Specimen

Beams were reinforced with steel stirrups with 6.3 mm of cross section, spaced 150 mm one another and out of the middle third. This procedure was adopted to eliminate the confining effect over GFRP bars which can cause an uprise of bond tension on the region of interest of the study. In the compressed area of the beam 8.0 mm steel bars were used in order to allow correct placement of GFRP bars and stirrups.

Due to the fabrication process of the GFRP Brazilian bars, two effective diameters (according to ASTM D7205-7205M, 2006) were present in the same batch: 13 and 14 mm. Those differences were considered during the test results analyses and the characteristics of each beam are summarized at Table 1. The nomenclature of each beam represents: the splice length, 25 or 40 diameters (related to the measured diameter), A or B series (considering that B is the replica series), presence of polyolefin fibers (F) or not (NF). Figure 2 shows recent casted beams.

Table 1: beam characteristics

Beam	Effective diameter (mm)	GFRP bar tensile strength (MPa)		Splice length (mm)	SCC tensile strength (MPa)		SCC compressive strength (MPa)		SCC elastic modulus (GPa)	
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
25ANF	13	843	59	330	4	1	75	7	28	1
25AF	13	859	51	340	3	1	68	11	27	1
40ANF	14	891	31	556	4	1	75	7	28	1
40AF	13	859	51	544	4	1	68	11	27	1

Figure 2: recent casted beams after curing process and with strain gauges cables identified and protected

Materials

All materials utilized during the research are available on Brazilian market, allowing that similar results are obtained by fellow researches, respected regional characteristics, specially related to natural materials, such as natural sand, coarse natural aggregate and filler. Each material are presented and main characteristics are described.

GFRP

The GFRP bars used on this work were donated by Stratus with a helicoidal surface appearance, with three diameters measured with caliper rule, namely: 13.2 mm, 13.6 mm and 13.9 mm, measured in the outer area of the superficial deformations of the bar, as seen in Figure 3. All GFRP bars were composed of a nucleus of E-Glass fibers, including superficial aspect fibers, and vinyl ester resin.

Figure 3: GFRP bars

Despite of physical differences between bars of different manufacturers, adopting the procedures predicted in ASTM D7205 allows comparing different bars using a normalized criteria in order to define a cross sectional area to GFRP bars and, consequently, compare more effectively bond characteristics, due to the impact of measurement criteria over bond tension results.

Three tests were made to define physical and tensile characteristics of GFRP bar: effective diameter, fiber volume composition using burning test, according to ASTM D3171-15, and tensile strength and elasticity modulus according to ASTM D7205. The results obtained by those tests are resumed and presented at Table 2.

Table 2: physical and tensile characteristics of GFRP bars according to ASTM D7205-06 and D3171-15

Measured diameter (mm)	Effective cross-sectional area (mm ²)	Effective diameter (mm)	Mean density (g/cm ³)	Volume of long fibers (%)	Volume of fibers in superficial aspect (%)	Volume of vinyl ester resin (%)	GFRP bar tensile strength (MPa)		Mean GFRP bar elasticity modulus (GPa)
							Mean	SD	
13.2	140	13	2.1	78	0.7	21	843	59	48
13.6	140	13	2.1	79	0.7	21	859	51	
13.9	160	14	1.9	73	0.7	27	891	31	

Tensile properties were obtained using MTS tensile test universal machine 311.11 with hydraulic grips with limit capacity of 1000 KN. Charge rate applied was 3.5 mm per minute. The tensile on

grips were set up to 0.8 psi, sufficient to avoid slipping of metallic anchor at the ends of GFRP bars. Those tests were made at Structures Laboratory of PUC-Rio.

Polyolefin fibers

Polyolefin fibers used on this research were from Concrifix manufacturer and donated by Geobruigg, with 50 mm long and with 0.5 mm of diameter, resulting in a form factor (λ) of 100. Tensile strength guaranteed by manufacturer were 618 MPa. In Figure 4 are shown the corrugated surface of polyolefin fiber used, increasing the mechanical bond between fibers and SCC.

Figure 4: MEV image with 100 x magnification (Donato, 2018)

Self-compacting concrete - SCC

To define the definitive mixture of the SCC for beams, nine experimental mixtures were carried out for a self-compacting concrete that showed appropriate behavior in terms of fluidity, resistance to segregation and workability with the inclusion of the polyolefin fibers. This factor has been considered of great importance, as the compressive resistance of concrete is one of the factors affecting the bond between the GFRP bars and concrete. Equally important was to ensure that this concrete did not present voids. Those voids in the region near the bar in GFRP would affect the mechanical interlock between GFRP bars a concrete, causing concentrated tensions and early localized bar surface ruptures, being difficult to eliminate variations arising from this factor.

Mixture number 5-corrected was adopted for the confection of the beams, described at Table 3. Observing the parameters provided in the Brazilian standard for self-compacting concrete, the spread for concrete with fibers presented 670 mm, therefore classified as SF 2. The t_{500} , defined as the time necessary to the spread of the mixture until it reach 500 mm of diameter over a standard table, for the concrete with fibers was 4 seconds, with apparent plastic viscosity VS 2 and visual stability class IEV 0, i.e., no evidence of segregation or exudation, as seen in Figure 5. The fiberless concrete presented 705 mm, therefore classified as SF 2, with t_{500} of 3 seconds, with apparent plastic viscosity VS 2 and visual stability class IEV 0, that is, without evidence of segregation or exudation. With the results obtained, this concrete can be used for most current applications.

Figure 5: Mixture 5 – used in fiber and non-fiber beams

For the definition of the maximum packaging, the lowest empty index between the coarse and fine aggregate was 18%, between fine aggregate and limestone filler was 30% and of the mixture between aggregates and fillers was 12%, resulting in a ratio of 60, 22 and 18% for coarse, fine and filler aggregates.

The concrete used in the beams showed a slight decrease in compression resistance with the addition of the fibers, but a similar elasticity module for concrete with or without fibers as seen in Table 3.

Table 3: SCC – Mixture 5 - Corrected

	N. of specimens elasticity modulus	Elasticity modulus (GPa)	SD (GPa)	N. of specimens for compressive strenght test	Compressive strenght (MPa)	SD (MPa)	N. of specimens for tensile strenght test	Tensile strenght (MPa)	SD (MPa)
NF	5	28.3	1.11	8	75.2	6.6	8	4.0	0.7
F	5	27.0	0.75	8	68.2	10.7	8	3.7	1.1

Experiment procedures

Instrumentation placement

To measure the bond tension a method proposed by Zemour et al (2018) was used. Ten strain gauges were placed across the splice length, at both sides of the GFRP bars reinforcement. The strain gauges used were Kyowa model KFGS-5-120-C1-11 L1M2R. They were also used for the tensile properties tests of GFRP bars. Placement of strain gauges are shown on Figure 6, dimensions on mm and related to GFRP bar diameter (ϕ). Position E is the only placed out of splice length in order to comparison.

Figure 6: strain gages placement at GFRP bars reinforcements

After definition of placement, GFRP surface were grinded manually using sanding paper until a smooth and uniform surface were obtained. After cleaned using 93° alcohol to remove all dust and grease, the strain gages were glued with methyl methacrylate resin taking care to ensure that the gage system of measurement was perfectly aligned with the long fibers core of bars. Gages were them protected with acetic silicon in order to protect strain gages from humidity and mechanical damages during the concrete pouring procedure. An additional layer of PVC material was placed over cured silicon layer, giving an extra protection against humidity and mechanical damages. Naturally, those

methods of protection create an interface between bars and concrete. However, those interferences were not considered relevant to the results obtained, since no system of measure can properly measure bond tension without interfering with interface bar-concrete. Figure 7 shows the strain gage after bonded over the GFRP surface and after totally protected against moisture and mechanical damage.

Figure 7: strain gages bonded and protected

Test Setup

Beams were tested at Military Institute of Engineering, Structures Laboratory, using a MTS Flextest 100 with capacity of 1000 KN. The tests were made under displacement control. A 0.6 mm/minute rate of displacement was defined at the first 2 mm of displacement and 1.22 mm/minute until rupture. A placement stage was defined at each 10 KN increment, in order to allow the crack measurement. Based on the Zemour et al (2018) work, a limit deflexion expected was 1/100, with respect to free length of beam. Figure 8 shows beam 25AF ready for test.

Figure 8: 25AF placed to test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Rupture pattern

All beams presented vertical cracks initiating at the middle third of the beam, from the tensioned region to the compressed region of beam. All beams presented the first crack at 30 KN. After the first vertical cracks, others with inclination to the centre of bending appeared according the vertical load increasing. The four beams presented rupture related to the rigid body rotation of the relatively short splices length. The failure pattern is compatible with those presented at Zemour et al. (2018), as shown in Figure 10. Concrete cover was expelled from beams in the region of splice. Figure 9 shows the rupture pattern.

Beams with bigger splice length presented lesser cracks than others. The presence of fibers on SCC didn't show any effect over number of cracks or rupture pattern.

Figure 9: rupture pattern

Figure 10: rupture pattern observed at this research and Zemour et al. (2018), respectively

All splice areas in the beams subjected to tests were exposed due to the cover concrete expelling. No signs of bar rupture were noticed. Near to the GFRP bars superficial conformation concrete residue was show at beams with bigger splice length. Beam 40AF presented shear of surface conformation, which was able to be noticed by white powder over GFRP bars. The crack pattern on the concrete cover spelled from the splice region was similar in all the four beams. Cracks transversal to the beam section united to the longitudinal ones caused the concrete cover speling, according to Figure 11. It indicates that GFRP bars were pressured against concrete cover.

Figure 11: concrete cover spelled from spliced area

Load vs bending behavior

Analysing the overall results, it is possible to observe that splice length and use of FRC had an increasing effect over the ultimate strength of beams. The ultimate load for 25 diameters splice length was 32% higher for beams with fibers. To the 40 diameters of splice length, the increase of ultimate load was 13% higher for those with fibers. All beams presented similar stiffness. Figure 12 shows the indicated analysis.

Figure 12: load vs bending behaviour

Load vs strain behaviour

Beam 25ANF presented at A and B placement incoherent results. This behaviour could be caused by low splice length, rupture of the strain gage cable during test or sleeping of the surface resin layer. Similar problems occurred to placements A, B and C to 40ANF beam and placement E of 40AF beam. The results are shown at Figure 13.

By analysing the graphs of the load-deformation, it is seen that the transfer of the traction tensions in bending of concrete to the GFRP bars at the time of the first crack load was more immediate for the non-fiber beams (beams 25ANF and 40ANF). There is an increased deformation of the GFRP bar for a constant applied load.

As expected, in a same beam, further the placement of a strain gage in relation to the splice, higher were the strain measured to a same load level.

Figure 13: Load vs strain behaviour

Splice effect over bond behaviour

Lower splice lengths resulted on higher bond tension, as expected. However, to beam 40AF an anomalous behaviour was observed.

Analysing the E placement, there was a localized slippage causing an increasing on the bond tension on the region immediate anterior, meaning, the region D supported an extra load to compensate the slippage at a further region. This behaviour can be observed at Figure 14, near to the 60 KN load area: at the same time that tension on region E drops abruptly, region D, subsequently to it, experience an increase on deformation, meaning that this region supported a higher load. A higher mean bond was registered due to this behaviour of compensation on beam 40AF.

Figure 14: 40AF beam with slippage at E placement e compensation mechanism on region D Comparing beams of similar composition, SCC with or without fibers of polyolefin, it was possible to register that bigger splice lengths result on lower bond tensions with a simultaneous increase on ultimate load, as shown on Figure 15.

Figure 15: Effect of splice length increasing over bond behaviour

Presence of polyolefin fibers on SCC over bond behaviour

The inclusion of 1% of polyolefin fibers on SCC over its volume caused a increase on bond behaviour of beams subjected to tests. Crack was not affected by the presence of fibers, due to its low elasticity modulus, lower then concrete.

The increase on bond tension in beams with 25 diameters of splice length, comparing 25ANF and 25AF, was of 73%. Comparing the mean bond tension of beams 40 ANF and 40AF, the results show a increase of 358% on bond tension at ultimate load to those beams. In general, it was possible to conclude that the inclusion of polyolefin fibers on SCC to the GFRP bars had a positive effect over bond behaviour, as demonstrated at Figure 16.

Figure 16: effect of 1% in volume of polyolefin fibers over bond

Discussions

When comparing the obtained results of this research with those of Zemour et al (2018), normalizing the bond tension dividing it for the square root of the compressive strength of concrete, the results obtained by those authors shows a 49% higher bond tensions, even utilizing higher diameters which expects that result on lower bond tension. It may indicate that Brazilian GFRP bar can be improved, with respect to the superficial aspect, when compared with international GFRP fabrication standards. Comparing the results obtained on this research with the predictions of bond behaviour according to ACI, AASHTO and CSA, the bond tension obtained are above the theoretical predictions of those normative, Figure 17, showing that superficial conformation of GFRP Brazilian bars can be increased, with gain of structural behaviour.

Figure 17: comparison of bond tension according to references

American and Canadian standards consider a better manufacturing control of quality and normalized productions characteristics. Those factors, meaning the uprise of minimum standards for FRP bar production, may result in a better structural behaviour of these materials.

CONCLUSIONS

After this research, it was concluded that higher splice lengths result on higher ultimate loads and smaller bond tensions. The inclusion of polymeric polyolefin fibers resulted on higher bond tensions, increasing the ultimate load of beams reinforced with GFRP bars. The splice regions can redistribute tension increases effectively through all splice length, caused by slippage.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.